

Ultrasound Characteristics and ACR-TIRADS Classification of Thyroid Incidentalomas in Adults Undergoing Imaging for Non-Thyroid Conditions In NAUTH, Nnewi

Michael E ARONU¹, Chinedu G AZUBIKE², Samuel I UDOBI¹, Catherine N OBASIKENE¹, Kelechi U OKOYE², Kelechi M UKE², Eric O UMEH¹

¹Department of Radiology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Nigeria. ²Department of Radiology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Background: Thyroid incidentalomas are nonpalpable, asymptomatic thyroid nodules that are discovered during Imaging or surgery unrelated to the thyroid gland. Thyroid incidentalomas are most commonly detected on ultrasound (US) performed for evaluation of extra-thyroidal structures. Presently, the prevalence of thyroid incidentalomas is increasing due largely to the availability of high-frequency ultrasound probes. Though these lesions are mostly benign, the risk of malignancy can be as high as 10-15%. **Objectives:** This study aims to characterize these lesions using their ultrasound features based on the ACR-TIRADS which has been proven to have higher specificity than other risk stratification systems. **Methodology:** This was a prospective study of 400 subjects, scanned using a Mindray ultrasound machine with a 5-12MHz linear array transducer. The data obtained from the study was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25.0. Continuous numerical variables (like age of the subjects, size of the nodules) were analyzed using both measures of central tendencies (mean and mode) and measures of dispersions (range and standard deviation). Discrete numerical variables, nominal categorical variables, as well as ordinal categories were analyzed by frequency and also presented in tables and charts. **Results:** The frequency of Thyroid incidentalomas in this study was 36.5%. It occurred in 46.59% of the females and 19.87% of the males. They frequent had cystic composition (63.78%), the most common echo-pattern was anechoic (62.75%) and they predominantly had a smooth outline (90.31%). Most were avascular (79.59%), few were hypovascular (20.41%), and none was hypervascular (0.00%). TIRADS 1 was the commonest category (50.68%) while TIRADS 5 was the least (5.48%).

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*Correspondence

Chinedu G. Azubike
Department of Radiology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital Nnewi, Nigeria.

Email: chineduazubike350@yahoo.com
Tel: +2348034793343

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Conclusions: This study supports the utility of routine ACR-TIRADS classification to guide further investigation and follow-up of thyroid incidentalomas.

Keywords: Thyroid Incidentaloma, Thyroid nodules, TIRADS, Ultrasonography.

INTRODUCTION

Following the development of high resolution and high precision ultrasound probes, the frequency of finding asymptomatic lesions in otherwise clinically normal thyroid glands has increased. This increased detection has contributed to heightened anxiety among patients and clinicians about potential malignancy. Consequently, there has been development of different risk stratification systems aimed at assessing the likelihood of malignancy or benignity of these lesions.

Thyroid incidentaloma is defined as an unsuspected, asymptomatic thyroid lesion that is discovered on an imaging study or during an operation unrelated to the thyroid gland.¹ Thyroid incidentaloma (TI) can also be defined as an unexpected, asymptomatic thyroid lesion fortuitously discovered during investigation of an unrelated condition.^{2,3,4,5,6} They represent a clinical challenge, thus, necessitating further investigation into the malignancy risk of each detected nodule.^{3,4}

Thyroid cancer is quite uncommon, accounting for about 1,000 new cases and 300 deaths in England and Wales per annum, while in the United States, there are about 12,000 new thyroid cancers and approximately 1000 deaths per annum.^{7,8}

The management of an incidental thyroid nodule is controversial. There is a dilemma between the need to avoid burdening the health care system with over-investigation of benign nodules and, the need to avoid the adverse effects that follow a delayed cancer diagnosis.⁹

Ultrasonography is the most accurate and cost-effective method of imaging the thyroid,^{10,11}

Ultrasound (US) is also non-invasive, readily available and non-ionizing, thus an ideal screening tool for nodular and diffuse thyroid disease.^{2,12} High-resolution US with its improved sensitivity has led to an increase in the frequency of detection of incidental thyroid nodules.^{10,13}

The risk of malignancy among detected TIs has been reported in some studies to be as high as 12.9%.³ US-guided fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is the test of choice for determining the nature of nodules. It is imperative to reduce the number of unnecessary FNAC while identifying clinically significant malignant nodules.

Ultrasound features of TI have been harnessed to create several risk stratification systems to identify nodules that warrant biopsy or follow-up, thus reducing the number of unnecessary FNAC.¹¹

The American College of Radiology (ACR) Thyroid Imaging Reporting and Data System (TIRADS) is an ultrasound-based risk stratification system (RSS) for thyroid nodules that was released in 2017.¹³ Research has shown that it has a higher specificity than other RSSs and reduces unnecessary biopsies of benign nodules compared with other RSSs by 19.9-46.5%.¹⁴

Thyroid incidentalomas are a global concern despite the dearth of research on the subject in Nigeria. With increasing detection due to more sensitive imaging, TIs often pose a clinical dilemma when found. To this end, many professional organizations have proposed ways to identify nodules that require active surveillance. For instance, in 2012, the American college of Radiology convened committees to investigate incidental thyroid nodules. By 2015, these committees published a white paper that presented an approach to TIs. Two years later (2017) ACR TIRADS was created.¹³

Thyroid incidentalomas has a risk of malignancy. This underscores the importance of early detection and acquisition of data that reflects prevalent local ultrasound characteristics. Such data can also be considered regionally to nationally representative, given the paucity of data on the subject in Nigeria.

Ultrasound (US) is the most sensitive imaging test for the thyroid gland.¹⁵ High-frequency transducers provide both deep ultrasound penetration and high-definition images.¹⁶ Ultrasonography is also affordable, and the TIRADS classification, a reliable risk stratification tool, is ultrasound-based. This makes US an effective screening modality for TIs and the preferred imaging for this study.¹⁷

The result obtained from this study can pave way for the establishment of local protocols in Nigerian setting for approaching TIs, which can in turn aid early detection of cancer.

The main objective of this study was to determine the ultrasound characteristics (patterns) of thyroid incidentalomas among adults in NAUTH, Nnewi and to classify the detected incidental thyroid nodules according to the risk of malignancy using the ACR-TIRADS classification.¹⁸

METHODOLOGY

This was a cross-sectional study of adults conducted over six (6) months (January 2023 - June 2023) conducted at Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital (NAUTH), in Nnewi North Local Government Area of Anambra state, Nigeria.

The sample size was calculated using the formula $N = Z^2 pq/e^2$.¹⁹ Using a prevalence of TIs estimated to be 33.4% by Tadesse *et al.*²⁰ and an attrition rate of 10%, the sample size was rounded up to 400. Consecutive convenience sampling method was used.

The inclusion criteria for this study are consenting adult subjects who are 18 years of age or older and consenting volunteers or patients referred for imaging to the Department of Radiology of NAUTH for reasons other than thyroid disease. Excluded were subjects less than 18 years, subjects with evidence of current thyroid disease, a visible or palpable thyroid mass, previous history of thyroid disease, thyroid surgery or radioiodine therapy. Also excluded were subjects with a family history of thyroid disease in a first degree relative, pregnant subjects and subjects who do not give consent for the study.

Approval for this study was obtained from the Ethical Committee of NAUTH. The data collected were treated with utmost confidentiality and this study was solely sponsored by the researchers. There was no conflict of interest or direct benefit to the subjects.

Consenting adult volunteers and patients who present for ultrasound examination of other parts of the body and who have fulfilled the inclusion criteria were recruited after consent was gotten. Clinical information of each subject were obtained and recorded.

Each of the subjects was scanned by the consulting radiologist with a second radiologist observing. Both of them were blinded to the patients' clinical details. At the end of each scan, both radiologists harmonized the ultrasound findings. A number assigned to each patient was used to identify the patient and match the clinical and radiological findings. The machine used for the scan was a Mindray ultrasound machine (model: DC-32 SN: 9Q-98000221; manufactured 18-08-2019) with a 5-12MHz linear array transducer.

Both lobes and the isthmus of the thyroid gland were scanned in the axial and longitudinal planes. Number, size and other ultrasound characteristics of thyroid nodules were recorded in the study data sheet.

The TIs were also classified according to their risk of malignancy using the ACR TIRADS. If a subject had multiple incidentalomas with different TIRADS classifications, the higher classification was assigned to the subject.

Ultrasound examinations were provided at no cost to participants, with departmental approval. The participants with TIs were referred for appropriate management based on the ACR TIRADS recommendations.

All the subjects recruited were included in the analyses as there was no case of incomplete data, nonresponse or outliers in the study.

The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), Version 25.0 (IBM Corp. Released 2017, IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.). Continuous numerical variables (like ages of the subjects, size of the nodules) were analyzed using both the

measures of central tendencies (mean and mode) and dispersions (range and standard deviation), and the results presented in frequency tables and charts. Discrete numerical variables (like the number of nodules) were analyzed using frequency. Nominal categorical variables (like sex, composition of nodules), binomial nominal categories (presence/absence of nodules), and ordinal categories (like TIRAD category) were analyzed by frequency and also presented in tables. Crosstabulations of appropriate variables were used for further analyses.

RESULTS

The total of 400 subjects whose data were analyzed, comprised 151 (37.75%) males and 249 (62.25%) females. The age range was 18-87 years, with a mean of 41.30 ± 14.62 years. The highest proportion of the respondents, 141 (35.25%) were within 29-39 years of age. This group contains 28.5% of the male population and 39.4% of the females. The least frequent were those above 84 years (1%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Bar chart illustrating age and sex distribution of the subjects

Of the 400 subjects, 254 (63.5%) had normal appearing thyroid glands, while 146 (36.5%)

had incidental thyroid nodules [Table 1]. The prevalence of TIs was thus 36.5%. It occurred in 116 (46.59%) of the females and 30 (19.87%) of the males.

Solitary nodules were found in the majority (73.9%) of the subject, followed by two nodules (17.80%) while 8.21% of subjects had more than two nodules. The least common location was the isthmus (6.85%). Subjects with nodules in the right lobe and left only (38.36%) were equally distributed.

Table 1. Distribution of TIs among the study participants

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Thyroid nodule		
No	254	63.50
Yes	146	36.50
Number of nodules per subject		
One	108	73.97
Two	26	17.80
Three	12	8.21
Location (n=146)		
Isthmus only	10	6.85
Left only	56	38.36
Multiple lobes	24	16.43
Right only	56	38.35

Most (63.78%) of the incidentalomas had a cystic composition, while the spongiform composition was the least common (1.02%). The most common echo-pattern was anechoic (62.75%), while the least common was the very hypoechoic (1.53%). The TIs were predominantly wider than tall (91.33%), with a smooth outline (90.31%). Following Doppler assessment, most were avascular (79.59%) while few were hypovascular (20.41%), and none was hypervascular (table 2).

Table 2. Ultrasound pattern of thyroid incidentaloma

Ultrasound features	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Composition		
Cystic	125	63.78
Mixed cystic and solid	24	12.24
Solid/Almost totally solid	45	22.96
Spongiform	2	1.02
Echogenicity		
Anechoic	123	62.75
Hypoechoic	44	22.45
Iso to Hyperechoic	26	13.27
Very Hypoechoic	3	1.53
Shape		
Wider than tall	179	91.33
Taller than wide	17	8.67
Margin		
Irregular	5	2.55
Smooth	177	90.31
ill-defined	14	7.14
Echogenic Foci		
Macrocalcification	16	8.16
Microcalcification	19	9.70
None/Large comet tail artifact	158	80.61
Rim-calcification	3	1.53
Vascularity		
Avascular	156	79.59
Hypovascular	40	20.41
Hypervascular	0	0.0
Others features		
Halo	6	3.06
Incomplete halo around the right	2	1.02
Nil	188	95.92

The commonest ACR-TIRADS category is the TIRADS 1 category, with 74 subjects (50.68%), of which 58 of these were seen in females and 16 in males, while the least represented classification was TIRADS 5, with only 8 subjects (5.48%). Table 3 and Figure. 2

Table 3. Classification of the thyroid incidentalomas using the ACR-TIRADS

ACR-TIRADS classification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
TIRADS 1	74	50.68
TIRADS 2	14	9.59
TIRADS 3	24	16.44
TIRADS 4	26	17.81
TIRADS 5	8	5.48
Total	146	100.0

Among the male subjects, the commonest ACR-TIRADS category was TIRADS 1 (53.3%), followed by TIRADS 4 (26.7%), while the least common category was TIRADS 5. Similarly, among the female subjects, the commonest category was TIRADS 1 (50%), however, in contrast to the males, this was followed by TIRADS 3 (17.2%), while the least common category was also TIRADS 5 (6.9% of females with TIs). (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Bar chart illustrating the distribution of ACR-TIRADS classification across males and females

DISCUSSION

There is little variation in the generally observed pattern/characteristics of thyroid incidentalomas among researchers. The incidental nodules were predominantly single in this study (73.97%), and this is in agreement with several other studies.^{2,21}

Regarding size, most of the detected incidental thyroid nodules in this study were <1cm. Other studies also report most TIs as subcentimetre in size.^{2,3,21} This is why they often escape clinical detection by palpation or self-observation by the patient.

Cystic nodules were also the commonest composition of the nodules seen in this study. The other predominant ultrasound features noted are smooth, well-circumscribed margins, anechoic echotexture and avascularity. Very hypoechoic echogenicity was the least common echogenicity. This is when a solid nodule is more hypoechoic than the strap muscles of the neck, and it is very suspicious for malignancy.⁹

Regarding distribution, there was no significant difference in right or left lobar predilection. For solitary nodules, 38.36% were equally noted in the right and left lobes. This is similar to the finding of Olusola-Bello *et al.*² In Ibadan, Nigeria, who also noted an equal distribution to both lobes (14.4%), while Taheri and his colleagues reported a significant right lobar preponderance, 31.4%, corroborating, a few other studies.^{3,22}

The isthmus was the least common location in this study, and other studies that report an isthmus-only location as the least common site have widely reported this.^{3,21}

Because most TIs are benign and not all nodules require FNAC and/or surgery, different risk stratification systems have been designed as noninvasive methods to identify which nodules warrant FNAC. The American College of Radiology TIRADS is one such method, and it was used to categorize the detected nodules in this study.

The commonest ACR TIRADS category in this study was TIRADS 1 (50.7%). ACR TIRADS 1 is reported to have a 0.3% risk of cancer.¹⁴ This is similar to what was reported by Olusola-Bello *et al.*² who used the TIRADS of Horvath and colleagues and reported that most of the lesions detected in their study were TIRADS 2. Horvath and colleagues' TIRADS 2 reportedly have a 0% probability for malignancy and loosely corresponds to the TIRADS 1 of the ACR.

The least common TIRADS category in this study was TIRADS 5 with 5.5% of subjects with TIs placed in this class.

Although the recommendation of the ACR TIRADS following detection of TI is follow-up Ultrasound or FNAC, clinicians typically would assess for thyroid function. Serum TSH assessment is considered by some as a good initial laboratory investigation for patients with incidental thyroid nodule(s).^{23,24} Some studies suggest that it may serve as an independent predictor of malignancy and as an adjunct to FNAC in predicting the risk of malignancy.^{25,26}

CONCLUSION

This study supports the utility of routine ACR-TIRADS classification to guide further investigation and follow-up of thyroid incidentalomas in routine radiologic practice in Nigeria as this can help reduce unnecessary FNAC in asymptomatic patients.

Limitation of the study

This study was limited to the use of ACR-TIRADS stratification based on the ultrasound characteristics to assess the risk of malignancy in the TIs and there was no histopathological confirmation of the benignity or malignancy of the lesions.

Recommendations

Studies involving the use of ACR-TIRADS stratification based on the ultrasound characteristics, serum TSH estimation and FNAC are recommended to assess the risk of malignancy in the TIs.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise, that could have influenced the design, conduct, objectivity or outcomes of this study.

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Authors' Contributions

Conceptualization and design of the study - CGA, MEA, EOU.

Data collection and technical support for imaging - CGA, CNO, KUO, MUO, KMU

Data analysis and interpretation - SIU, MEA.

Revision of manuscript for intellectual content. - CGA, MEA, SIU, EOU.

Drafting of the manuscript - CGA, CNO, KUO, KMU.

All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

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